

Reproducibility Log: Small research ecosystems in large international public policies: tracing an infrastructurally mediated pathway from CroRIS to Overton

This document accompanies the article *Small research ecosystems in large international public policies: tracing an infrastructurally mediated pathway from CroRIS to Overton*.

The Overton dataset used in this study is subject to a third-party licence (Overton Researcher Agreement) and cannot be shared publicly. Researchers may obtain access to equivalent data directly from Overton (<https://www.overton.io>) under similar conditions. All aggregated statistics and code used to produce the analyses are available from the author upon reasonable request.

1. CroRIS affiliation data retrieval

Objective

To obtain standardized institutional names (including English variants where available) for Croatian public research organizations, in order to match them with Overton affiliation data.

The exported table serves as an authority list for institutional name matching against Overton.

Data source: CroRIS API

The data were retrieved from the Croatian Research Information System (CroRIS) via its public API.

The endpoint used returns a list of all scientific/research institutions registered in CroRIS, in HAL-formatted JSON. The relevant objects are contained in the `_embedded$sustanove` element of the response.

Implementation

Data extraction and filtering were implemented in R (version 2025.09.1) using:

- `httr` for HTTP requests,
- `jsonlite` for parsing JSON into R data structures,
- `writexl` for exporting the resulting data frame to an Excel file.

All filtering was performed with base R functions (`subset()` and logical indexing).

Filtering of institutions

From the full list of institutions returned by the CroRIS API, only records that met all of the following conditions were retained:

1. Ownership type - public institutions only

The CroRIS field `tipVlasnistva` (ownership type) was used to identify publicly owned institutions. Records were kept only if `tipVlasnistva` was equal to "public" (case-insensitive check in the code). Conceptually, this step restricts the sample to publicly owned research institutions.

2. Type of institution - universities, public research institutes, and faculties

The field `vrstaUstanove` is a nested object containing, among others, the subfield `naziv`, which labels the institutional type in Croatian.

Only institutions whose `vrstaUstanove$naziv` belonged to one of the following categories were retained:

- `sveučilište` (university)
- `javni znanstveni institut` (public research institute)
- `fakultet` (faculty, i.e. constituent unit of a university)

3. This restriction focuses the analysis on core public higher education and research institutions that are most relevant for the study.

Name fields and language variants

CroRIS provides multiple name fields per institution. In the exported table, the following are used:

- `puniNaziv` - full official name in Croatian,
- `nazivEn` - official English name (short form), where available,
- `mzoId` - national institutional identifier assigned by the Ministry of Science and Education,
- `vrstaUstanove` (label in Croatian) - indicating whether the institution is a university, public research institute, or faculty.

For non-Croatian readers, the Croatian full name is preserved as the legal/official reference form, while the English name, when present, is used to facilitate matching with Overton affiliation strings, which are predominantly in English.

Institutions for which `nazivEn` is missing are retained; these can be matched using Croatian forms or through additional manual harmonisation if needed.

Output

The final dataset contains one row per institution and the following columns:

- `Naziv_HR` - official full name in Croatian (`puniNaziv`),
- `Naziv_EN` - English name (`nazivEn`), when available,
- `MZO_broj` - institutional identifier (`mzoId`),
- `Vrsta_ustanove` - institutional type (Croatian label; university, public research institute, or faculty).

This table is exported as an Excel file and used as the authoritative list of Croatian public higher education and research institutions for subsequent matching with Overton affiliation data.

Exported table saved as `croris_research_institutes_public.xlsx` in the project data folder.

Code:

```

library(httr)
library(jsonlite)
library(writexl)

base_url <- "https://www.croris.hr/ustanove-api"
url <- paste0(base_url, "/upisnik-ustanova/ustanova/znanstvena")

res <- GET(url, accept("application/hal+json"))
stop_for_status(res)

txt <- content(res, as = "text", encoding = "UTF-8")

dat <- fromJSON(txt)

ustanove <- dat[["_embedded"]][["ustanove"]]

ustanove <- subset(
  ustanove,
  !is.na(tipVlasnistva) & tolower(tipVlasnistva) == "public"
)

vrsta_vec <- ustanove$vrstaUstanove$naziv

wanted_vrste <- c(
  "sveučilište",
  "javni znanstveni institut",
  "fakultet"
)

mask_vrsta <- !is.na(vrsta_vec) & vrsta_vec %in% wanted_vrste
ustanove <- ustanove[mask_vrsta, ]

cat("Broj ustanova nakon oba filtra:", nrow(ustanove), "\n")

df_out <- data.frame(
  Naziv_HR = ustanove$punaNaziv,
  Naziv_EN = ustanove$nazivEn,
  MZO_broj = ustanove$mzoId,
  Vrsta_ustanove = vrsta_vec[mask_vrsta],
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)

out_path <- file.path(
  "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data",
  "croris_research_institutes_public.xlsx"
)

```

```
write_xlsx(df_out, out_path)

cat("Datoteka spremljena u:\n", out_path, "\n")
```

2. Overton data retrieval and matching to CroRIS institutions

Objective

To identify policy-cited scholarly articles with at least one author affiliated with a Croatian public university, faculty, or public research institute, and to link these articles to standardized institutional identifiers from CroRIS.

Data source: Overton

Policy-cited articles were retrieved from Overton using the web interface. The following filters were applied:

- Has author in country: Croatia

The resulting set contains articles for which Overton's affiliation geocoding links at least one author to an institution located in Croatia. The records were exported from Overton as a CSV file ([articles-metadata-2025-12-01.csv](#)) containing, among others, the following fields:

- bibliographic metadata: title, DOI, journal, publication date, document type, publisher
- policy-related metadata: policy citation counts and related indicators
- author-affiliation information: concatenated author and affiliation strings stored in the Authors column

Implementation in R

Subsequent processing and matching to CroRIS institutions were implemented in R (version 2025.09.1) using:

- readr for importing the Overton CSV export,
- dplyr, tidyr and purrr for data manipulation and iteration over institutions,

- stringr for normalisation and pattern matching in affiliation strings,
- writextl / write_csv for exporting derived datasets.

For reproducibility, each Overton record was assigned a technical row identifier:

- row_id = row_number(),
- authors_clean = lower-cased version of Authors with redundant whitespace removed (str_squish + str_to_lower).

Normalisation of institutional names

The CroRIS authority table described in the previous section was used as the reference list of Croatian public research organisations. For each institution, two normalised name variants were constructed:

- name_hr_clean - full official Croatian name (Naziv_HR) in lower case with extra whitespace removed,
- name_en_clean - English name (Naziv_EN), where available, similarly normalised.

These variants were reshaped into a long format so that each row corresponds to a single institution-name combination (Croatian or English). Institutions without an English name were retained and matched using only the Croatian form.

Matching procedure

Matching proceeded by searching for each normalised CroRIS name within the Overton author-affiliation strings:

1. For each row in the CroRIS authority list, the corresponding name_clean value (Croatian or English) was taken as a search pattern.
2. Using stringr::str_detect with fixed(), a case-insensitive fixed-string search was performed over authors_clean in the Overton data.
3. Whenever a match was found, a record was created linking the Overton row_id to the CroRIS institution (MZO_broj, Naziv_HR, Naziv_EN).
4. All such records were combined into a long-format table in which each row represents a pair (article, CroRIS institution) whenever at least one of the institution's name variants appears in the Authors field.

The resulting match table was then left-joined back to the full Overton export by row_id, producing a dataset ([overton_matched_full.csv](#)) that contains, for each article-institution pair, both:

- the institutional identifiers and names derived from CroRIS, and
- the complete set of Overton metadata for the underlying article.

Derived datasets and filters

From the full match table, two derived datasets were created:

- Article-institution pairs ([overton_article_institution_pairs.csv](#)): a deduplicated table retaining one row per unique combination of DOI, Title, MZO_broj, Naziv_HR, and Naziv_EN. This table is used for counts and distributions of policy-cited articles by institution.
- DOI list for further Overton queries ([croRIS_matched_dois_for_overton.csv](#)): a list of unique, non-missing DOIs for all articles that could be linked to at least one CroRIS-listed public institution.

Conceptually, the CroRIS authority list acts as a filter on the Overton export: only articles whose author-affiliation strings contain at least one institutional name from CroRIS (in Croatian or English form) are retained for further analysis. The DOI list derived from this filtered subset is then re-submitted to Overton's DOI search interface to obtain richer metadata and policy context not included in the initial export.

Limitations and considerations

The matching procedure relies on exact fixed-string detection within concatenated author-affiliation strings. This approach is transparent and reproducible but sensitive to:

- spelling variants and abbreviations of institutional names,
- incomplete or ambiguous affiliation strings in Overton,
- cases where only departmental or hospital names are recorded without the parent university or institute.

These limitations are taken into account in the interpretation of results, and the CroRIS authority list provides a controlled baseline that can be extended with additional name variants in future iterations if needed.

Code:

```
library(readxl)
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(stringr)
library(purrr)
library(tidyr)
library(writexl)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"

cro_path <- file.path(base_dir, "croRIS_research_institutes_public.xlsx")
ov_path <- file.path(base_dir, "articles-metadata-2025-12-01.csv")
doi_out <- file.path(base_dir, "croRIS_matched_dois_for_Overton.csv")
matches_out <- file.path(base_dir, "Overton_croRIS_matched.xlsx")

cro <- read_xlsx(cro_path) %>%
  mutate(
    name_hr_clean = str_to_lower(str_squish(Naziv_HR)),
    name_en_clean = str_to_lower(str_squish(Naziv_EN))
  )

cro_names <- cro %>%
  select(MZO_broj, Naziv_HR, Naziv_EN, name_hr_clean, name_en_clean) %>%
  pivot_longer(
    cols = c(name_hr_clean, name_en_clean),
    values_to = "name_clean",
```

```

    values_drop_na = TRUE
  ) %>%
  distinct(MZO_broj, Naziv_HR, Naziv_EN, name_clean)

ov <- read_csv(ov_path) %>%
  mutate(
    row_id = row_number(),
    # prilagodi naziv stupca ako nije "Authors"
    authors_clean = str_to_lower(str_squish(Authors))
  )

find_matches_for_name <- function(name_str) {
  which(str_detect(ov$authors_clean, fixed(name_str, ignore_case = TRUE)))
}

matches_list <- map(seq_len(nrow(cro_names)), function(i) {
  idx <- find_matches_for_name(cro_names$name_clean[i])
  if (length(idx) == 0) return(NULL)

  tibble(
    row_id = ov$row_id[idx],
    MZO_broj = cro_names$MZO_broj[i],
    Naziv_HR = cro_names$Naziv_HR[i],
    Naziv_EN = cro_names$Naziv_EN[i]
  )
})

matches <- bind_rows(matches_list)

ov_matched <- matches %>%
  left_join(ov, by = "row_id")

doi_list <- ov_matched %>%
  distinct(DOI) %>%
  filter(!is.na(DOI) & DOI != "")

write_csv(doi_list, doi_out)

articles_by_institution_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_article_institution_pairs.csv")
ov_matched_full_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_matched_full.csv")

write_csv(articles_by_institution, articles_by_institution_path)
write_csv(ov_matched, ov_matched_full_path)

cat("Gotovo.\n",
    "DOI lista:", doi_out, "\n",
    "Parovi rad-institucija (CSV):", articles_by_institution_path, "\n",
    "Full match (CSV):", ov_matched_full_path, "\n")

```

3. Analysis of the matched CroRIS–Overton dataset for articles

3.1. Distribution of policy-cited articles across institutions

To visualise the distribution of policy-cited articles across institutions, the article–institution pairs table (`overton_article_institution_pairs.csv`) was imported into R and the institutional English names (`Naziv_EN`) were normalised by collapsing multiple spaces and converting all characters to upper case, yielding a standardised label `Naziv_EN_std`. The data were then grouped by the CroRIS institutional identifier (`MZO_broj`) and `Naziv_EN_std`, and the number of unique DOIs per group (`n_articles`) was computed using `n_distinct(DOI)`. This summary table was saved as `institution_article_counts_EN_ALLCAPS.csv` and used to generate a horizontal bar chart (one bar per institution) with `Naziv_EN_std` on the y-axis and the count of unique policy-cited articles on the x-axis, implemented in `ggplot2` with `geom_col()` and `coord_flip()`.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(stringr)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
pairs_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_article_institution_pairs.csv")

pairs <- read_csv(pairs_path) %>%
  mutate(
    Naziv_EN_std = Naziv_EN |>
```

```

str_squish() |>
str_to_upper()
)

inst_counts <- pairs %>%
group_by(MZO_broj, Naziv_EN_std) %>%
summarise(
n_articles = n_distinct(DOI),
.groups = "drop"
) %>%
arrange(desc(n_articles))

write_csv(inst_counts,
file.path(base_dir, "institution_article_counts_EN_ALLCAPS.csv"))

ggplot(inst_counts,
aes(x = reorder(Naziv_EN_std, n_articles), y = n_articles)) +
geom_col() +
coord_flip() +
labs(
x = "Name of the institution",
y = "Number of unique policy-cited articles (DOI)",
) +
theme_minimal(base_size = 11)

```

Graph:

3.2. Publications over time

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(lubridate)
library(ggplot2)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
ov_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_matched_full.csv")

ov <- read_csv(ov_path)

ov_year <- ov %>%
  mutate(
    pub_date = as.Date(`Published on`),
    pub_year = year(pub_date)
  ) %>%
  filter(
    !is.na(DOI), DOI != "",
    !is.na(pub_year)
  ) %>%
  group_by(pub_year) %>%
  summarise(
    n_articles = n_distinct(DOI),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  arrange(pub_year)

write_csv(ov_year,
          file.path(base_dir, "articles_by_publication_year.csv"))

ggplot(ov_year, aes(x = pub_year, y = n_articles)) +
  geom_line() +
  geom_point() +
  labs(
    x = "Publication year",
    y = "Number of unique policy-cited articles (DOI)",
```

```
) +  
theme_minimal(base_size = 11)
```

Graph:

3.3. Retrieving policy citations for CroRIS-matched DOIs and computing time-to-policy

To obtain citation-level links between CroRIS-matched articles and policy documents, the list of unique DOIs ([croRIS_matched_dois_for_overton.csv](#)) was queried in Overton via the *Articles* interface. Because the user interface becomes unstable with very large inputs, the DOI list was manually split into batches of up to 1,000 identifiers, which were pasted into the “Search for identifiers” dialog. For each batch, the results page was used to export *policy cites of the first 1,000 outputs to CSV*, producing files named according to the DOI range (e.g.

1-1000 articles-2025-12-02.csv, 1001-2000 articles-2025-12-02.csv, ...) and stored in a dedicated folder (`export_doi_to_policy_citation`). Each row in these exports corresponds to a single article–policy citation pair and includes the article DOI, article publication date (`Published on`), and the policy document date (`Cited by date`), alongside basic metadata on the citing organisation.

All batch files were then processed in R using `readr`, `dplyr`, `lubridate`, `stringr` and `ggplot2`. Within the folder `export_doi_to_policy_citation`, all CSVs matching the pattern `articles-2025-12-02.csv` were loaded, row-bound, and deduplicated with `distinct()`, resulting in a single dataset `policy_all`. For each article–policy pair, the article publication date (`Published on`) and policy citation date (`Cited by date`) were parsed as dates, and the time lag was computed as `lag_days = policy_date - article_date` and `lag_years = lag_days / 365.25`, retaining only records with non-missing DOIs and both dates. Aggregation by DOI yielded, for each article, the number of distinct citing policy documents and the mean and median lag in years, saved as `policy_citation_lag_by_doi.csv`. Overall summary statistics across all citation events (total number of policy citations and articles, mean, median and interquartile range of `lag_years`) were saved in `policy_citation_lag_summary_overall.csv`. Finally, a histogram of the time-to-policy distribution was drawn for lags between 0 and 30 years using `geom_histogram(binwidth = 1)`, with a dashed vertical line marking the median lag, to visualise how quickly CroRIS-matched articles tend to be cited in policy documents.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(lubridate)
library(stringr)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data/export_doi_to_policy_citation"

policy_files <- list.files(
  base_dir,
  pattern = "articles-2025-12-02\\.csv$",
  full.names = TRUE
)

policy_files
policy_all <- policy_files %>%
  lapply(read_csv) %>%
  bind_rows() %>%
  distinct()

glimpse(policy_all)
```

```

policy_lag <- policy_all %>%
  mutate(
    article_date = as.Date('Published on'),
    policy_date = as.Date('Cited by date'),
    article_year = year(article_date),
    policy_year = year(policy_date),
    lag_days = as.numeric(policy_date - article_date),
    lag_years = lag_days / 365.25
  ) %>%

  filter(!is.na(DOI),
         DOI != "",
         !is.na(article_date),
         !is.na(policy_date))
lag_by_doi <- policy_lag %>%
  group_by(DOI) %>%
  summarise(
    n_policy_docs = n_distinct('Cited by source ID'),
    mean_lag_years = mean(lag_years, na.rm = TRUE),
    median_lag_years = median(lag_years, na.rm = TRUE),
    .groups = "drop"
  )

write_csv(lag_by_doi,
          file.path(base_dir, "policy_citation_lag_by_doi.csv"))

lag_summary_overall <- policy_lag %>%
  summarise(
    n_policy_citations = n(),
    n_articles = n_distinct(DOI),
    mean_lag_years = mean(lag_years, na.rm = TRUE),
    median_lag_years = median(lag_years, na.rm = TRUE),
    p25_lag_years = quantile(lag_years, 0.25, na.rm = TRUE),
    p75_lag_years = quantile(lag_years, 0.75, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

write_csv(lag_summary_overall,
          file.path(base_dir, "policy_citation_lag_summary_overall.csv"))
library(ggplot2)
policy_lag_trim <- policy_lag %>%
  filter(lag_years >= 0, lag_years <= 30)

median_lag <- median(policy_lag_trim$lag_years, na.rm = TRUE)

ggplot(policy_lag_trim, aes(x = lag_years)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 1, boundary = 0, closed = "left") +
  geom_vline(xintercept = median_lag, linetype = "dashed") +
  scale_x_continuous(
    limits = c(0, 30),

```

```

breaks = seq(0, 30, by = 5)
) +
labs(
  x = "Lag between article publication and policy citation (years)",
  y = "Number of policy citations",
) +
theme_classic(base_size = 11)

```

Graph:

Table X. Summary of time-to-policy for CroRIS-matched articles

Statistic	Value
Number of policy citations	16,330
Number of distinct articles (DOIs)	5,994
Mean lag (years)	5.79
Median lag (years)	3.88

25th percentile (years)	1.80
75th percentile (years)	7.53

3.4. Top 20 publishers of Croatian-authored articles cited in policy

To analyse the publishers of Croatian-authored scholarly articles cited in public policy, I used the list of 6,022 unique DOIs derived from the CroRIS–Overton matching step (`croRIS_matched_dois_for_overton.csv`) and submitted the entire DOI column in a single batch to the *Articles* search interface in Overton. Using the “Search for identifiers” option, I pasted the full list of DOIs into the identifiers dialog and ran the query. From the resulting set of articles, I used the export function to download a single article-level metadata file (`6022_articles-metadata-2025-12-02.csv`), which contains, for each DOI, the article title, journal, publication date (`Published on`), policy citation count, document type (`Type`), publisher (`Publisher`), and basic author information.

For the publisher-level analysis, this CSV was imported into R, and the data were processed using `readr` and `dplyr`. First, I confirmed that the file contained 6,022 distinct DOIs and 409 distinct publishers. I then grouped the data by `Publisher` and, for each publisher, counted the number of unique DOIs (`n_articles = n_distinct(DOI)`). To obtain the share of policy-cited articles published by each publisher, I divided `n_articles` by the total number of distinct DOIs (6,022) and multiplied by 100, producing a percentage share per publisher. The resulting table, sorted in descending order of `n_articles`, summarises the distribution and concentration of publishers of Croatian-authored scholarly articles that have been cited in policy documents.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
art_path <- file.path(base_dir, "6022_articles-metadata-2025-12-02.csv")

articles <- read_csv(art_path)

n_distinct(articles$DOI)
n_distinct(articles$Publisher)

publisher_summary <- articles %>%
  filter(
    !is.na(DOI), DOI != "",
    !is.na(Publisher), Publisher != ""
  ) %>%
```

```

group_by(Publisher) %>%
summarise(
  n_articles = n_distinct(DOI),
  .groups = "drop"
) %>%
arrange(desc(n_articles)) %>%
mutate(
  total_articles = sum(n_articles),
  share          = n_articles / total_articles,
  share_percent  = round(100 * share, 2)
)

write_csv(
  publisher_summary,
  file.path(base_dir, "publisher_share_policy_cited_articles.csv")
)

top_publishers <- publisher_summary %>%
  slice_max(n_articles, n = 20)

ggplot(top_publishers,
  aes(x = reorder(Publisher, n_articles), y = n_articles)) +
  geom_col() +
  coord_flip() +
  labs(
    x = "Publisher",
    y = "Number of Croatian-authored policy-cited articles",
  ) +
  theme_minimal(base_size = 11)

```

Graph:

3.5. Distribution of cited scholarly articles by Croatian authors across journal subject areas

To describe the subject area profile of Croatian-authored articles cited in policy, I used Overton’s built-in journal subject classification. After running the DOI-based article search for the 6,022 CroRIS-matched outputs, I generated the Overton *Articles report* and extracted the “Journal subjects” table summarising the number of articles in each subject area. This table was manually transcribed into a CSV file ([overton_journal_subjects_from_report.csv](#)) and imported into R. Using [dplyr](#), I computed the share of articles per subject area by dividing the count of articles in each category by the total of 6,022 articles, and visualised the distribution (top 20 subject areas) with a horizontal bar chart in [ggplot2](#).

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(stringr)
```

```

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
subj_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_journal_subjects_from_report.csv")

subjects <- read_csv(subj_path)

subjects_summary <- subjects %>%
  rename(
    Journal_subject = with_journal_subject,
    n_articles = count
  ) %>%
  mutate(
    Journal_subject = str_squish(Journal_subject)
  ) %>%
  arrange(desc(n_articles)) %>%
  mutate(
    total_articles = sum(n_articles),
    share = n_articles / total_articles,
    share_percent = round(100 * share, 2)
  )

write_csv(
  subjects_summary,
  file.path(base_dir, "journal_subject_distribution_policy_cited_articles.csv")
)

top_subjects <- subjects_summary %>%
  slice_max(n_articles, n = 20)

ggplot(top_subjects,
  aes(x = reorder(Journal_subject, n_articles), y = n_articles)) +
  geom_col() +
  coord_flip() +
  labs(
    x = "Journal subject area (Overton)",
    y = "Number of Croatian-authored policy-cited articles",
  ) +
  theme_minimal(base_size = 11)

```

```

concentration_summary <- subjects_summary %>%
  mutate(rank = row_number()) %>%
  summarise(
    top10_share = sum(n_articles[rank <= 10]) / sum(n_articles),
    top20_share = sum(n_articles[rank <= 20]) / sum(n_articles),
    median_count = median(n_articles)
  ) %>%
  mutate(
    top10_share_percent = round(100 * top10_share, 2),
    top20_share_percent = round(100 * top20_share, 2)
  )

```

concentration_summary

Graph:

Table X. Concentration of journal subject areas for policy-cited Croatian articles

Statistic	Value
Share of subject assignments in top 10 subjects	21.5 %
Share of subject assignments in top 20 subjects	33.9 %
Median number of articles per subject	17

3.6. Distribution of Croatian-authored scholarly articles by access type (Overton)

To describe the access status of Croatian-authored articles cited in policy, I used Overton's open access classification. From the Articles report for the 6,022 CroRIS-matched DOIs, I exported the summary table of open access categories (`overton_open_access_status.csv`), which reports, for each `oa_status` (gold, green, hybrid, bronze, diamond, closed, unknown), the number of associated articles. This table was imported into R and processed with `dplyr`: for each access type, I computed the total count of articles and its share in the full set of 6,022 articles (`share_percent = count / sum(count) * 100`). The resulting distribution, saved as `open_access_distribution_policy_cited_articles.csv` and visualised as a pie chart in `ggplot2`, shows the relative prevalence of closed and various open access modes among Croatian-authored articles that have been cited in policy documents.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
oa_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_open_access_status.csv")
```

```

oa <- read_csv(oa_path)

oa_summary <- oa %>%
  mutate(
    total_articles = sum(count),
    share          = count / total_articles,
    share_percent  = round(100 * share, 1),
    label          = paste0(oa_status, " (", share_percent, "%)"),
    # opcionalno: kontrola redosljedja u legendi
    oa_status = factor(
      oa_status,
      levels = c("gold", "green", "diamond", "hybrid", "bronze", "closed", "unknown")
    )
  )

ggplot(oa_summary, aes(x = "", y = share, fill = oa_status)) +
  geom_col(width = 1, color = "white") +
  coord_polar(theta = "y") +
  scale_fill_manual(
    name = "Access type",
    values = c(
      gold   = "#FFD700",
      green  = "#1B9E77",
      diamond = "#66C2A5",
      hybrid = "#7570B3",
      bronze = "#CD7F32",
      closed = "#999999",
      unknown = "#CCCCCC"
    )
  ) +
  theme_void(base_size = 19)

```

Graph:

4. Analysis of the dataset for policy documents

4.1. Top 20 policy sources citing CroRIS-matched articles

Using the Overton “policy cites” exports (`* articles-2025-12-02.csv`), I combined all files into a single dataset (`policy_all`) and grouped records by `Cited by source` to compute, for each policy organisation, the total number of citation events (`n_citations`), distinct policy documents (`n_policy_docs`) and distinct Croatian-authored articles cited (`n_articles`). I then ranked sources by `n_articles`, selected the top 20 organisations (`slice_max(n_articles, n = 20, with_ties = FALSE)`), and visualised the number of cited articles per source in a horizontal bar chart using `ggplot2`.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data/export_doi_to_policy_citation"
```

```
policy_files <- list.files(  
  base_dir,  
  pattern = "articles-2025-12-02\\.csv$",  
  full.names = TRUE  
)
```

```
policy_all <- policy_files %>%  
  lapply(read_csv) %>%  
  bind_rows() %>%  
  distinct()
```

```
glimpse(policy_all)
```

```
policy_by_source <- policy_all %>%  
  filter(!is.na(`Cited by source`), `Cited by source` != "") %>%  
  group_by(`Cited by source`) %>%  
  summarise(  
    n_citations = n(),  
    n_policy_docs = n_distinct(`Cited by source ID`),  
    n_articles = n_distinct(DOI),  
    .groups = "drop"  
  ) %>%  
  arrange(desc(n_articles))
```

```
top_sources <- policy_by_source %>%  
  slice_max(n_articles, n = 20, with_ties = FALSE)
```

```
ggplot(top_sources,  
  aes(x = reorder(`Cited by source`, n_articles),  
      y = n_articles)) +  
  geom_col() +  
  coord_flip() +  
  labs(  
    x = "Policy source (organisation)",  
    y = "Number of Croatian-authored articles\ncited by this source",  
  ) +  
  theme_minimal(base_size = 11)
```

Graph:

4.2. Policy documents citing CroRIS-matched articles by organisation sector

Using the combined article–policy citation dataset (`policy_all`), I grouped records by `Cited by organisation sector` and, for each sector, calculated the number of citation events, distinct policy documents, and distinct Croatian-authored articles, as well as each sector's share of all citing policy documents. The resulting summary table (`policy_citations_by_organisation_sector.csv`) was then visualised as a pie chart in `ggplot2`, showing the relative contribution of different sectors (e.g. government, international organisations, NGOs) to policy citations of CroRIS-matched articles.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(lubridate)
library(stringr)
library(ggplot2)
```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data/export_doi_to_policy_citation"
```

```
policy_files <- list.files(
  base_dir,
```

```

pattern = "articles-2025-12-02\\.csv$",
full.names = TRUE
)

policy_all <- policy_files %>%
  lapply(read_csv) %>%
  bind_rows() %>%
  distinct()

glimpse(policy_all)

policy_by_sector <- policy_all %>%
  filter(!is.na(`Cited by organisation sector`),
         `Cited by organisation sector` != "") %>%
  group_by(`Cited by organisation sector`) %>%
  summarise(
    n_citations = n(), # article-policy pairs
    n_policy_docs = n_distinct(`Cited by source ID`), # distinct policy documents
    n_articles = n_distinct(DOI), # distinct cited articles
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  arrange(desc(n_policy_docs)) %>%
  mutate(
    total_policy_docs = sum(n_policy_docs),
    share_policy_docs = n_policy_docs / total_policy_docs,
    share_policy_docs_percent = round(100 * share_policy_docs, 1),
    label = paste0(`Cited by organisation sector`,
                   " (", share_policy_docs_percent, "%)")
  )

policy_by_sector

write_csv(
  policy_by_sector,
  file.path(base_dir, "policy_citations_by_organisation_sector.csv")
)

ggplot(policy_by_sector,
  aes(x = "", y = share_policy_docs, fill = `Cited by organisation sector`)) +
  geom_col(width = 1, color = "white") +

```

```

coord_polar(theta = "y") +
geom_text(aes(label = paste0(share_policy_docs_percent, "%")),
          position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5),
          size = 6) +
labs(
  fill = "Organisation sector",
) +
theme_void(base_size = 16)

```

Graph:

4.3. Policy documents citing CroRIS-matched articles\nby organisation type

Code:

```

library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(lubridate)
library(stringr)
library(ggplot2)

```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data/export_doi_to_policy_citation"
```

```

policy_files <- list.files(
  base_dir,
  pattern = "articles-2025-12-02\\.csv$",
  full.names = TRUE
)

policy_all <- policy_files %>%
  lapply(read_csv) %>%
  bind_rows() %>%
  distinct()

glimpse(policy_all)

policy_by_type <- policy_all %>%
  filter(!is.na(`Cited by organisation type`),
         `Cited by organisation type` != "") %>%
  group_by(`Cited by organisation type`) %>%
  summarise(
    n_citations = n(), # article-policy pairs
    n_policy_docs = n_distinct(`Cited by source ID`), # distinct policy documents
    n_articles = n_distinct(DOI), # distinct cited articles
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  arrange(desc(n_policy_docs)) %>%
  mutate(
    total_policy_docs = sum(n_policy_docs),
    share_policy_docs = n_policy_docs / total_policy_docs,
    share_policy_docs_percent = round(100 * share_policy_docs, 1),
    label = paste0(`Cited by organisation type`,
                  " (", share_policy_docs_percent, "%)")
  )

policy_by_type

write_csv(
  policy_by_type,
  file.path(base_dir, "policy_citations_by_organisation_type.csv")
)

ggplot(policy_by_type,
  aes(x = "", y = share_policy_docs, fill = `Cited by organisation type`)) +
  geom_col(width = 1, color = "white") +
  coord_polar(theta = "y") +

```

```

geom_text(aes(label = paste0(share_policy_docs_percent, "%"),
  position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5),
  size = 3) +
labs(
  fill = "Organisation type",
) +
theme_void(base_size = 14)

```

Graph:

4.4. SDGs referenced by policy documents citing CroRIS-matched articles

To characterise the SDG profile of citing policy documents, I used the policy-level Overton export (`export-2025-12-02 policy.csv`) and the `Related to SDGs` field, splitting multiple annotations per document on the “|” separator, extracting SDG-level labels (e.g. “SDG 3”), and counting, for each SDG, the number and share of distinct policy documents (`policy_documents_by_SDG.csv`). I then visualised this distribution as a treemap in **ggplot2** using **treemapify**, mapping each SDG to its official UN colour and scaling the area of each tile proportionally to the number of policy documents associated with that goal.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(stringr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(treemapify)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
policy_path <- file.path(base_dir, "export-2025-12-02 policy.csv")

policy <- read_csv(policy_path)

policy_sdgs <- policy %>%
  filter(!is.na(`Related to SDGs`), `Related to SDGs` != "") %>%
  separate_rows(`Related to SDGs`, sep = "\\|") %>%
  mutate(
    Related_to_SDGs = str_squish(`Related to SDGs`),
    SDG = str_extract(Related_to_SDGs, "SDG \\d+")
  ) %>%
  filter(!is.na(SDG))

sdg_summary <- policy_sdgs %>%
  group_by(SDG) %>%
  summarise(
    n_policy_docs = n_distinct(`Overton id`),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  mutate(
    total_policy_docs = sum(n_policy_docs),
    share_docs = n_policy_docs / total_policy_docs,
    share_docs_percent = round(100 * share_docs, 1),
    SDG_num = as.integer(str_extract(SDG, "\\d+"))
  ) %>%
  arrange(SDG_num)

write_csv(
  sdg_summary,
  file.path(base_dir, "policy_documents_by_SDG.csv")
)

sdg_colors <- c(
  "1" = "#E5243B", # No poverty
```

```
"2" = "#DDA63A", # Zero hunger
"3" = "#4C9F38", # Good health and well-being
"4" = "#C5192D", # Quality education
"5" = "#FF3A21", # Gender equality
"6" = "#26BDE2", # Clean water and sanitation
"7" = "#FCC30B", # Affordable and clean energy
"8" = "#A21942", # Decent work and economic growth
"9" = "#FD6925", # Industry, innovation and infrastructure
"10" = "#DD1367", # Reduced inequalities
"11" = "#FD9D24", # Sustainable cities and communities
"12" = "#BF8B2E", # Responsible consumption and production
"13" = "#3F7E44", # Climate action
"14" = "#0A97D9", # Life below water
"15" = "#56C02B", # Life on land
"16" = "#00689D", # Peace, justice and strong institutions
"17" = "#19486A" # Partnerships for the goals
```

```
)
```

```
ggplot(
  sdg_summary,
  aes(
    area = n_policy_docs,
    fill = factor(SDG_num),
    label = paste0(SDG, "\n", share_docs_percent, "%")
  )
) +
  geom_treemap() +
  geom_treemap_text(
    size = 0.5,
    colour = "white",
    place = "centre",
    grow = TRUE
  ) +
  scale_fill_manual(
    values = sdg_colors,
    guide = "none"
  ) +
  labs(
  ) +
  theme_void(base_size = 8)
```

Graph:

4.5. Volume of policy output vs. use of Croatian research by ministry

For this part of the analysis, I combined two Overton-derived summary tables aggregated by source: `overton_CROministries.csv`, which reports the total number of Overton-indexed policy documents per Croatian ministry, and `overton_croatian_articles_cited_in_CROministries.csv`, which reports, for the same ministries, the number of documents containing at least one citation to a Croatian-authored article affiliated with CroRIS institutions. In R, I merged these tables by ministry name, computed for each ministry the share of its Overton-indexed policy documents that cite Croatian research (`share_docs_with_citation = n_docs_citing_hr_articles / n_docs_total_overton`), and visualised the result with a scatter plot where the x-axis represents total policy output and the y-axis the proportion of documents citing Croatian-authored articles, with ministry labels added for easier interpretation.

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(scales)
library(ggrepel)
```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
```

```
citing_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_croatian_articles_cited_in_CROministries.csv")
all_path <- file.path(base_dir, "overton_CROministries.csv")
```

```
citing_docs <- read_csv(citing_path) %>%
  rename(
    Ministry = authors,
    n_docs_citing_hr_articles = count
  )
```

```
all_docs <- read_csv(all_path) %>%
  select(authors, count) %>%
  rename(
    Ministry = authors,
    n_docs_total_overton = count
  )
```

```
ministry_impact <- all_docs %>%
  full_join(citing_docs, by = "Ministry") %>%
  mutate(
    n_docs_citing_hr_articles = if_else(
      is.na(n_docs_citing_hr_articles), 0L, n_docs_citing_hr_articles
    ),
    share_docs_with_citation = n_docs_citing_hr_articles / n_docs_total_overton,
    share_percent = round(100 * share_docs_with_citation, 2),
    label = if_else(n_docs_citing_hr_articles > 0, Ministry, "")
  ) %>%
  arrange(desc(n_docs_total_overton))
```

```
ggplot(ministry_impact,
  aes(x = n_docs_total_overton,
    y = share_docs_with_citation)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_text_repel(
    aes(label = label),
    size = 3,
    box.padding = 0.4,
    point.padding = 0.2,
    min.segment.length = 0,
    max.overlaps = Inf
  ) +
  scale_y_continuous(labels = scales::percent_format(accuracy = 1)) +
  labs(
    x = "Total Overton-indexed policy documents",
```

```
y = "Share that cite Croatian-authored articles"
)+
theme_minimal(base_size = 16) +
theme(
  plot.margin = margin(t = 5, r = 100, b = 5, l = 20),
  axis.title.y = element_text(margin = margin(r = 55))
)+
coord_cartesian(clip = "off")
```

Graph:

